

New records of *Gyraulus rossmaessleri* (Gastropoda: Planorbidae) in the Czech Republic

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Populations of the freshwater snail *Gyraulus rossmaessleri* (Auerswald, 1852) (Gastropoda, Planorbidae) were found at 4 sites in the Meandry Smědé Nature Reserve (Northern Bohemia, Czech Republic). In Bohemia this species has not been found for last 25 years and the nearest localities with its known occurrence in the past are situated about 100 km to the south-west.

Introduction

Gyraulus rossmaessleri (Auerswald, 1852) is according to MEIER-BROOK (1983) an European species with very restricted Central European range but GLÖER (2002) mentioned holarctic distribution. In comparison with other species of genus *Gyraulus* this gastropod inhabits especially temporary pools and wetlands. Conchs of *G. rossmaessleri* are often similar to non-angled conchs of *G. acronicus* (A. Férussac, 1807) and dissection is useful and often necessary for determination.

Distribution in the Czech Republic

Gyraulus rossmaessleri is mentioned from the Czech Republic for the first time in MÁCHA (1963) from Silesia. Revision of material in different collections (National Museum of Prague, private collection of P. Kuchař – owner L.R. Kolouch) showed that this species occurred in the past also in North-Western Bohemia and in Eastern Bohemia (BERAN 2002). New sites with occurrence of this species in the Litovelské Pomoraví Protected Landscape Area (Central Moravia) mentioned BERAN (2000). Recently it is known from the Litovelské Pomoraví PLA (Central Moravia), Poodří PLA, Ostrava surroundings, Opava surroundings (all Silesia) (BERAN 2002). Distribution of this gastropod in the Czech

Republic in different periods is shown in BERAN (2002).

G. rossmaessleri in the Czech Republic inhabits different types of temporary wetlands – alder carrs, swamps overgrown with *Glyceria* spp., *Carex* spp., small temporary pools or canals in floodplain forest or meadows. All these types of wetlands are endangered especially outside of protected sites by different human activities (e.g., river regulation, soil draining).

New records

New sites with occurrence of *G. rossmaessleri* were found in the Meandry Smědé Nature Reserve (Northern Bohemia) near Czech – Poland border in 2004. These new sites are mentioned below. Data are as follows – geographical coordinates, code of the mapping field for faunistic grid mapping (cf. PRUNER & MÍKA 1996), name of the nearest settlement, description of the site, altitude, name of finder, number of collected individuals, date of investigation): 50°59'18" N, 15°01'42" E, 5056, Filipovka, temporary ditch near border of Meandry Smědé NR 400 m from the railway station Filipovka, 235 m, L. Beran, 6 ex., 25 April 2004; 50°59'06" N, 15°01'24" E, 5056, Filipovka, sedge marsh 10 m outside of the Meandry Smědé NR

